

1 **Complementary non-sputum diagnostic testing for tuberculosis in people with HIV by**
2 **using oral swab PCR and urine lipoarabinomannan detection**

3
4 Running title: Oral swabs and urine LAM for TB diagnosis

5
6 Adrienne E. Shapiro^{1,2}, Alaina M. Olson³, Lara Kidoguchi¹, Xin Niu⁴, Zinhle Ngcobo⁵, Zanele P.
7 Magcaba⁵, Mduduzi W. Ngwane⁵, Grant R. Whitman³, Kris M. Weigel³, Rachel C. Wood³, Doug
8 P.K. Wilson^{5,6}, Paul K. Drain^{1,2}, Gerard A. Cangelosi^{1,3,4*}

9
10 ¹Department of Global Health, University of Washington, Seattle, WA, USA; ²Department of
11 Medicine, Division of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, University of Washington, Seattle, WA,
12 USA; ³Department of Environmental and Occupational Health Sciences, University of
13 Washington, Seattle, WA, USA; ⁴Department of Epidemiology, University of Washington, Seattle,
14 WA, USA; ⁵Umkhuseli Research and Innovation Management, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa;
15 ⁶University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa

16
17 *Corresponding author: Gerard Cangelosi, Dept. of Environmental and Occupational Health
18 Sciences, Box 351618, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195. Email: gcang@uw.edu

19
20 Key words: tuberculosis, oral swabs, diagnostic, urine, non-sputum, lipoarabinomannan (LAM),
21 OSA, tongue swabs.

22

23 **Abstract**

24

25 Testing for mycobacterial lipoarabinomannan (LAM) in urine is a practical but insensitive
26 alternative to sputum testing to diagnose tuberculosis (TB) in people with HIV (PWH). Here, we
27 evaluated urine LAM testing alongside PCR-based tests for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB)
28 DNA in tongue swabs. We hypothesized that the two non-sputum samples would deliver
29 complementary, not redundant, results. The study included 131 South African patients of whom
30 64 (48.1%) were confirmed to have TB by GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra (Xpert Ultra) or culture
31 analysis of sputum. 120 patients (91.6%) were co-infected with HIV and 130 yielded a valid
32 urine LAM result (Alere DETERMINE LAM Ag). Tongue swab samples were tested by IS6110-
33 targeted qPCR with a Cq (quantification cycle) cutoff of 32. Relative to reference sputum testing
34 (TB culture and Xpert Ultra), combined urine LAM and oral swab testing (either sample positive)
35 was significantly more sensitive than either non-sputum sample alone (57% sensitivity for
36 combined testing vs. 35% and 39% sensitivity for urine LAM and tongue swabs; $p = 0.01$ and
37 0.04 , respectively). Specificity of combined testing (neither sample positive) was 97%. On
38 average, tongue swab-positive participants had higher sputum signal strength than urine-LAM
39 positive participants, as measured by sputum Xpert Ultra Cq value ($p=0.037$). A subset of
40 tongue swabs ($N=18$) were also tested by using Xpert Ultra, which reproduced true positive and
41 true negative IS6110 qPCR results, and resolved the two false-positive tongue swabs. With
42 further development, tongue swabs and urine may feasibly serve as complementary non-
43 sputum samples for diagnosis of TB in PWH.

44

45 **Introduction**

46 Tuberculosis disease (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB), remains a
47 major cause of illness and death in people with HIV (PWH) (1). The standard sample for TB
48 diagnosis is sputum, which can be difficult for PWH to produce and insensitive in some patients.
49 The availability of noninvasive alternatives to sputum testing would substantially improve TB
50 care for PWH (2, 3).

51 Most TB transmission occurs between development of disease (including asymptomatic
52 disease) and initiation of treatment. Active case finding, in which high-risk populations are
53 actively screened and TB is identified and treated earlier than by relying on symptomatic self-
54 presentation, could reduce transmission in many populations (4, 5). Examples of such
55 populations include contacts of known TB cases, occupants of institutions such as prisons and
56 hospitals, people with HIV, and residents in high-burden areas. Sputum collection is a significant
57 barrier to active screening. For example, only ~20% of participants in a Brazilian prison cohort
58 were able to provide quality sputum specimens (6, 7).

59 Even in the context of passive TB diagnosis, many patients cannot routinely produce
60 sputum for testing. PWH and children often require induction (nebulization), an invasive
61 procedure. For all of these reasons, Fauci and Eisinger (2018) have called for “twenty-first
62 century diagnostic technologies that can detect Mtb in a variety of clinical specimens from
63 multiple body sites in addition to sputum” (3). Alternative, non-invasive sampling strategies
64 could help identify the “missing millions” of TB cases that currently go undetected each year (8).

65 Immunoassays for mycobacterial lipoarabinomannan (LAM) in urine are potential
66 alternatives to sputum testing. However, the single WHO-approved urine LAM test (by
67 Alere/Abbott) lacks sensitivity. Although next-generation urine LAM tests are in development or
68 evaluation, even best-performing tests of the LAM analyte alone may not be optimally sensitive
69 to detect TB disease in PWH (9-12).

70 In search of an alternative non-sputum sample type, we and others have shown that
71 MTB DNA can be detected by oral swab analysis (OSA) (13-22). In OSA, the dorsum of the
72 tongue is brushed with a sterile swab, and the collected material is tested for MTB DNA. This
73 non-invasive, non-sputum sample collection approach can be applied to any patient, in any
74 setting, including tertiary hospital, outpatient clinic, remote health point, or home and community
75 settings.

76 Despite their promise, to date neither OSA nor urine LAM testing has proven to be
77 sensitive enough to detect all TB in PWH. We hypothesize that sensitivity is limited for different
78 reasons in the two methods. For example, pulmonary disease may be required to deposit
79 enough MTB in the mouth for detection by OSA, whereas a very high total mycobacterial burden,
80 including extrapulmonary disease, may be required for transrenal passage of MTB glycolipids
81 into urine. Therefore, a parallel approach using both methods may detect more TB cases in
82 PWH than either method alone. The current study was conducted to assess the
83 complementarity of the two methods.

84

85 **Methods**

86 Participant enrollment: South African adults (age ≥ 16 years) with HIV (regardless of
87 symptoms), or adults with TB symptoms or a positive sputum Xpert Ultra TB test, were
88 consecutively enrolled into the prospective PROVE-TB cohort at Harry Gwala Regional Hospital
89 (formerly Edendale Hospital) and affiliated clinics in Pietermaritzburg, South Africa between
90 October 2019 and February 2021. Persons who had received TB treatment for more than 24
91 hours were excluded.

92 The PROVE-TB cohort was developed and recruited as a platform for evaluating
93 noninvasive TB diagnostic tests and algorithms in a high-TB-burden setting. Adults receiving
94 usual care were recruited into the cohort at the time of hospital admission if they had HIV,

95 irrespective of TB symptoms or reason for admission. To enrich the cohort for persons with TB
96 disease, in order to conduct early-stage validation tests of novel diagnostic tests, adults in the
97 hospital or affiliated clinics with a new positive sputum Xpert Ultra result were also recruited into
98 the cohort, prior to initiating treatment.

99 All cohort participants received clinically indicated diagnostic examinations and testing
100 as determined by their treating clinicians, and these tests were used for clinical decision-making.
101 These included sputum Xpert Ultra, urine LAM, chest Xrays, and other blood tests and imaging,
102 as well as other testing directed at the primary admitting diagnosis. For persons in whom
103 clinicians were investigating TB, clinically indicated samples were collected and these results
104 were used to create the TB reference definition. For cohort participants not being clinically
105 investigated for TB, supplemental research sputum and urine samples were collected for Xpert
106 Ultra, culture, and urine LAM testing. Urine LAM testing was repeated for research purposes
107 and interpreted by a single reader, even if a LAM result had been obtained as part of clinical
108 care. Xpert and culture testing were performed in the same laboratory and under the same
109 conditions, regardless of indication (clinical investigation or research screening). Blood was
110 collected for CD4+ T-cell measurement (in persons with HIV), biomarker testing (including C-
111 reactive protein) and biorepository storage for later assays.

112 Clinical, laboratory, and demographic data were collected from participants and
113 abstracted from clinical charts. Sputum, urine, tongue swab, and blood samples were collected
114 at bedside and transported to the on-site laboratory for processing and analysis. Study data
115 were collected and managed using REDCap electronic data capture tools hosted at the Institute
116 of Translational Health Sciences. All participants provided written informed consent. This study
117 was approved by the ethical committees of the University of KwaZulu-Natal (BREC #BE475/18)
118 and the University of Washington (Study 9092).

119 Sample collection and analysis. From each participant, one expectorated sputum sample
120 was tested directly with GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra (Xpert Ultra, Cepheid, Sunnyvale, California,

121 USA) in the South African National Health Laboratory System (NHLS) laboratory at Harry Gwala
122 Regional Hospital. A second expectorated sputum sample for *M. tuberculosis* complex culture
123 was decontaminated with 1.25% N-acetyl-L-cysteine sodium hydroxide and processed according
124 to the MGIT testing protocol. *M. tuberculosis* complex liquid culture was conducted in the
125 Provincial NHLS laboratory using the BACTEC MGIT960 system (Becton-Dickinson
126 Microbiology System, Sparks, MD, USA).

127 A TB case was defined as a participant with either a positive sputum Xpert Ultra or a
128 positive sputum TB culture result (reference testing). A non-TB case was defined as a
129 participant with no positive sputum results. Negative sputum testing could comprise either
130 negative sputum Xpert Ultra and TB culture results, or a negative result (either Xpert Ultra or
131 culture) with the second sputum test result unavailable or invalid. Spontaneously voided urine
132 samples were tested for the presence of LAM using the Alere LAM antigen lateral-flow assay
133 (Alere Determine™ TB LAM Ag test, Abbott Laboratories, Chicago, IL, USA). The LAM test was
134 interpreted according to the manufacturer's instructions. A result of 1+ or higher according to the
135 manufacturer's visual read-out card was considered positive. Two tongue dorsum swabs
136 (Copan FLOQSwabs; Copan Italia, Brescia, Italy) were collected into separate tubes as
137 described previously (14, 15). Briefly, study staff ran the swab over the length and breadth of
138 the anterior 2/3 of the subject's tongue. Pressure was sufficient to slightly bend the swab shafts.
139 Samples were collected for 15-20 seconds while rotating the swab throughout. Swab heads with
140 collected material were snapped off into 2 mL screw cap tubes containing 0.5 mL sterile TE
141 buffer.

142 Swabs in buffer were stored frozen at -80 °C and transported to the Cangelosi
143 Laboratory for blinded analysis. Persons performing the OSA amplification were blinded to the
144 results of the sputum tests and urine LAM test. Thawed samples were manually processed
145 (Qiagen), concentrated by ethanol precipitation, and tested by IS6110-targeted qPCR. Swab
146 analysis methods were as described previously (14, 15) with the following modifications. Post-

147 boil samples were eluted from the swab head then split, 250 μ L reserve and 250 μ L for
148 immediate processing by volume-scaled-lysis (300 μ L each of Qiagen Buffer AL and 100%
149 ethanol). The qPCR protocol used New England BioLabs® Inc Luna® Universal Probe qPCR
150 Master Mix, and the ethanol-precipitated samples were rehydrated in 5 μ L TE buffer prior to
151 master mix addition. Cq values were recorded and results were calculated using two Cq
152 thresholds (38 as described previously (14, 15), and a more stringent value of 32).

153 In addition to manual OSA, a subset of samples were tested by using Xpert Ultra. These
154 samples were defined as “reserve” (leftover half-samples that had been refrozen after boiling) or
155 “duplicate” (separate swab samples collected at the same time and immediately stored). Both
156 reserved and duplicate samples (total N=18) were paired with manual OSA data. Samples were
157 tested by Xpert Ultra by using either of two methods described elsewhere (22), depending on
158 whether they were reserve or duplicate. Briefly, in one method (“boil method”), 200 μ L half-
159 samples, which were previously boiled and stored frozen, were thawed and received 2.2 mL TE
160 buffer. The samples were shaken on a lab vortexer (GENIE® SI-0236 Vortex-Genie 2 Mixer,
161 120V) on setting 10 for 10-15 seconds, then allowed to sit at ambient temperature (20C to 22C)
162 for 5 minutes and then shaken for an additional 10-15 seconds, before allowing them sit for
163 additional 10 minutes at ambient temperature. The entire recoverable sample volume was
164 transferred into the sample reservoir of the Xpert Ultra cartridge for analysis. Samples were
165 recorded as positive for MTB if GeneXpert software returned any positive result.

166 Duplicate samples, which were not previously boiled, were processed by the “single
167 swab SR method” described in reference (22). These 0.5-mL samples were thawed at ambient
168 temperature for 30 min, then supplemented with 0.3 mL TE and 1.6 mL of Cepheid Sample
169 Reagent (SR). The samples were vortexed for 10-15 seconds, and incubated for 5 minutes
170 before vortexing for an additional 10-15 seconds. The samples were further incubated for
171 additional 10 minutes before the entire sample volume was transferred to the cartridges.

172 Analysis of results. Sensitivities and specificities of index methods (swabs, urine LAM,
173 and parallel testing) were calculated relative to the reference method (positive sputum Xpert
174 Ultra or positive sputum culture). When comparing sensitivity and specificity values, significance
175 was calculated by z score (two-tailed, 0.05 significance level).

176
177

178 **Results**

179 We enrolled 131 participants (45% female, median age 36 years) who provided all
180 sample types for index and reference testing. 120 (92%) participants had HIV. Participant
181 characteristics are summarized in **Table 1**. Of the 131 participants, 64 (49%) were TB cases by
182 reference testing (**Figure 1**).

183 Relative to the sputum reference standard, OSA using manual qPCR conducted on a
184 single swab, with a Cq cutoff of 38, was significantly more sensitive than urine LAM
185 (respectively, 42/64 [67%] vs. 22/63 [35%]; $p = 0.005$). However, OSA was less specific than
186 urine LAM (respectively, 52/67 [78%] vs. 67/67 [100%]; $p < 0.001$). When a more stringent Cq
187 cutoff of 32 was applied to define a positive OSA result, OSA and urine LAM performed similarly
188 (respectively, 25/64 [39%] vs. 22/63 [35%] sensitive, and 65/67 [97%] vs. 67/67 [100%] specific)
189 (**Table 2**).

190 When evaluating parallel (combination) non-sputum testing, a positive index test was
191 defined as being either urine LAM-positive or OSA-positive. With parallel testing, sensitivity
192 improved to 36/63 [57%], significantly better than urine LAM alone ($p=0.01$) or OSA alone
193 ($p=0.04$). Of the 36 participants who were true positive by non-sputum methods, 11 were
194 positive by both methods while 25 were positive by only one or the other (14 by OSA and 11 by
195 urine LAM; **Figure 1**). Specificity of the combined method remained high at 65/67 (97%).

196 In a secondary analysis, we tested the hypothesis that OSA (an airway sample) would
197 correlate more closely with sputum signal strength than urine-LAM (a transrenal sample).
198 Sputum signal strength was based on sputum Xpert Ultra quantitative readouts from the
199 IS6110/IS1081 combined probe (Cq values, which are inversely proportionate to signal
200 strength). In participants who were OSA-positive regardless of urine LAM results, sputum Cq
201 values were slightly lower (stronger signal) than in participants who were urine-LAM positive
202 regardless of OSA results (**Table 3**; $p = 0.037$ by unpaired, one-tailed T test). The difference
203 became more significant ($p = 0.019$ by unpaired, one-tailed T test) when comparing participants
204 who were positive only by OSA to those who were positive only by urine LAM, despite smaller
205 numbers within these mutually exclusive categories (**Table 3**).

206 The manual qPCR method used in Table 1 performed well in past OSA studies (14, 15,
207 21) but is impractical for routine diagnostic use. Therefore, in an additional secondary analysis
208 we used the semi-automated Cepheid GeneXpert MTB/RIF Ultra platform to test a subset of 18
209 frozen swab samples from the current study (11 true positives with the strongest qPCR signals
210 by OSA, 5 true negatives by OSA, and the 2 false positives by OSA). The 11 true positive
211 samples selected for this analysis had manual OSA Cq values ranging from 19.9 to 32.0
212 (average = 27.1 ± 4.0). Xpert Ultra detected 10 of 11 true positives by manual qPCR OSA (the
213 11th sample had an invalid Xpert Ultra result) and correctly excluded all 5 true negatives. It also
214 correctly excluded the 2 false positives by manual qPCR OSA (**Table 4**).

215

216

217 **Discussion**

218 Many PWH struggle to produce sputum (sputum-scarce) and/or have low MTB cell
219 counts in sputum (paucibacillary) (2, 3). This study tested the hypothesis that parallel testing of
220 two different non-sputum samples can deliver complementary, not redundant diagnostic
221 information, and thereby serve as an alternative to sputum testing for at least some patients.

222 Recent years have seen advancements in urine LAM testing for sputum-scarce or
223 paucibacillary patients. LAM is an MTB cell wall glycolipid that can pass transrenally into urine.
224 In some patients, most notably PWH with low CD4 counts, LAM is found in the urine in sufficient
225 quantities to enable rapid detection by using lateral flow tests such as the Alere Determine™ TB
226 LAM Ag. However, the sensitivity of urine LAM tests remains suboptimal (9-12).

227 We hypothesized that OSA can improve TB diagnosis in paucibacillary and sputum-
228 scarce patients when used in combination with urine LAM testing. The physiological bases for
229 urine LAM testing (transrenal passage of a mycobacterial glycolipid) and OSA (deposition of
230 MTB cells and/or DNA on the tongue dorsum during cough, exhalation, or spontaneous sputum
231 production) are likely to differ from each other. Urine LAM may work best in cases that involve
232 some hematogenous spread of MTB beyond the airways, while OSA may be best in pulmonary
233 TB. The strengths and limitations of the two methods may therefore complement each other.

234 The results were consistent with this hypothesis. When the more stringent Cq cutoff of
235 32 was applied, a diagnostic criterion of positivity in either urine LAM or OSA was significantly
236 more sensitive than either method alone. Specificity was acceptable at 97% and was the
237 minimum of the individual test specificities, but not lower in combination.

238 When using quantitative sputum Xpert Ultra readouts as measures of sputum signal
239 strength, patients who were exclusively OSA-positive were found to have significantly higher
240 loads than patients who were exclusively urine-LAM positive. This is consistent with the view
241 that OSA is a bronchial tree (airway) sample, in contrast to urine LAM which is a bloodstream

242 (circulatory) sample. Thus, the two samples may complement each other because they focus on
243 separate body compartments.

244 This study focused on the biological question of complementarity. Limitations associated
245 with implementation were only partially addressed. While swab sample collection has minimal
246 resource requirements, the manual qPCR method for OSA requires laboratory facilities,
247 specialized equipment and skilled technical operators, so is not practical for routine clinical
248 laboratory use in its current form. However, analysis of a subset of 18 samples with the near
249 point-of-care Xpert Ultra platform suggested that similar results can be obtained with automated
250 tests (with the caveat that the true-positive samples chosen for this subset were strongly
251 positive by manual qPCR). Therefore, this strategy can in theory be applied in any setting with
252 access to both Alere Determine™ TB LAM AG and Xpert Ultra.

253 The Xpert Ultra portion of this study had two limitations: it focused on patients with
254 strong manual OSA signals, and the number of participants was small. Recently, a separate
255 study of OSA using the Xpert Ultra test (22) was conducted in Uganda within a larger cohort of
256 participants with possible TB (N = 183, including 58 PWH). In that study, overall sensitivity of
257 OSA using Xpert Ultra, relative to a sputum microbiology reference standard, was 77.8% (95%
258 CI 64.4-88.0). Specificity was 100.0% (95% CI 97.2-100.0). Among the 58 PWH in the Uganda
259 study, sensitivity was 55.6% (95% CI 21.2-86.3) with no loss of specificity. Those results may
260 better reflect what users of OSA can expect when using Xpert Ultra as a molecular assay, at
261 least in some settings. Other automated amplification platforms intended for near-point-of-care
262 or point-of-care use are also in development and have the potential to be configured for TB OSA.

263 Another implementation concern is the requirement for two laboratory tests per patient.
264 In context, the same limitation often applies to current sputum-dependent strategies, because
265 paucibacillary and sputum-scarce patients often require multiple sampling and testing attempts
266 to confirm TB. To conserve resources, the two specimens could be collected simultaneously
267 and then tested in a staged reflex algorithm. Swabs, which are easy and inexpensive to collect

268 from any patient, can be collected and stored concurrently (dry or in TE buffer) with the
269 collection of all urine samples. If a patient's urine is positive for LAM, then that is diagnostic of
270 TB and there is no need to test the stored swab. If the urine LAM test is negative, then the swab
271 can be tested to avoid having to recall the patient for sputum induction.

272 In conclusion, our results indicate that tongue swabs and urine can serve as
273 complementary non-sputum samples for improved diagnosis of TB in PWH. With further
274 optimization to improve sensitivity, this approach may be considered as a fully non-sputum
275 strategy for detecting TB in patients who are unable to produce adequate sputum for testing, or
276 in settings where sputum collection isn't practical. Given the diverse spectrum of TB in adults
277 and children, it is unlikely that any single sampling method is ideal for all case types. Thus, it is
278 potentially useful when two non-sputum methods can complement each other as seen here.

279 **Acknowledgements**

280

281 This work was supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (#INV-004527, OPP
282 1213054), by NIH grants R01AI139254 and U54EB027049. REDCap at ITHS is supported by
283 the National Center For Advancing Translational Sciences of the National Institutes of Health
284 under Award Number UL1 TR002319. AES is supported by NIH (NIAID) K23A140918. We are
285 grateful to Cepheid, Inc., for providing research-use-only Xpert Ultra test kits, and to Copan
286 Italia for providing swabs.

287

288 This work was presented in part at virtual TB Science 2021, (Abstract #TBS-LB-2021-02134)

289

290

291

292 **Literature cited**

- 293
- 294
- 295 1. World Health Organization. Global Tuberculosis Report 2020.
- 296 2. UNITAID. 2017. Tuberculosis diagnostics technology and market landscape - 5th edition.
- 297 World Health Organization.
- 298 3. Fauci AS, Eisinger RW. 2018. Reimagining the Research Approach to Tuberculosis. *Am J*
- 299 *Trop Med Hyg* 98:650-652.
- 300 4. Shapiro AE, Ross JM, Yao M, Schiller I, Kohli M, Dendukuri N, Steingart KR, Horne DJ.
- 301 2021. Xpert MTB/RIF and Xpert Ultra assays for screening for pulmonary tuberculosis
- 302 and rifampicin resistance in adults, irrespective of signs or symptoms. *Cochrane*
- 303 *Database Syst Rev* 3:Cd013694.
- 304 5. Marks GB, Nguyen NV, Nguyen PTB, Nguyen T-A, Nguyen HB, Tran KH, Nguyen SV, Luu
- 305 KB, Tran DTT, Vo QTN, Le OTT, Nguyen YH, Do VQ, Mason PH, Nguyen V-AT, Ho J,
- 306 Sintchenko V, Nguyen LN, Britton WJ, Fox GJ. 2019. Community-wide Screening for
- 307 Tuberculosis in a High-Prevalence Setting. *New England Journal of Medicine* 381:1347-
- 308 1357.
- 309 6. Bourdillon PM, [Gonçalves](#) CC, Pelissari DM, Arakaki-Sanchez D, Ko AI, Croda J, Andrews
- 310 JR. 2017. Increase in Tuberculosis Cases among Prisoners, Brazil, 2009-2014. *Emerg*
- 311 *Infect Dis* 23:496-499.
- 312 7. Carbone, A.d.S.S., Paião, D.S.G, Sgarbi RVE, Lemos EF, Cazanti RF, Ota MM, Junior AL,
- 313 Bampi JVB, Elias VPF, Simionatto S, Motta-Castro ARC, Pompilio McA, de Oliveira SMdV,
- 314 Ko AI, Andrews JR, Croda J. 2015. Active and latent tuberculosis in Brazilian correctional
- 315 facilities: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 15:24.
- 316 8. Pande T, Vasquez NA, Cazabon D, Creswell J, Brouwer M, Ramis O, Stevens RH,
- 317 Ananthakrishnan R, Qayyum S, Alphonsus C, Oga-Omenka C, Nafade V, Sen P, Pai M.
- 318 2020. Finding the missing millions: lessons from 10 active case finding interventions in
- 319 high tuberculosis burden countries. *BMJ Global Health* 5:e003835.
- 320 9. Broger T, Sossen B, du Toit E, Kerkhoff AD, Schutz C, Ivanova Reipold E, Ward A, Barr DA,
- 321 Mace AI, Trollip A, Burton R, Ongarello S, Pinter A, Lowary TL, Boehme C, Nicol MP,
- 322 Meintjes G, Denkinger CM. 2019. Novel lipoarabinomannan point-of-care tuberculosis
- 323 test for people with HIV: a diagnostic accuracy study. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*
- 324 19:852-861.
- 325 10. Bjerrum S, Schiller I, Dendukuri N, Kohli M, Nathavitharana RR, Zwerling AA, Denkinger
- 326 CM, Steingart KR, Shah M. 2019. Lateral flow urine lipoarabinomannan assay for
- 327 detecting active tuberculosis in people living with HIV. *The Cochrane database of*
- 328 *systematic reviews* 10:CD011420.
- 329 11. Nathavitharana R, Lederer P, Richardson M, Bjerrum S, Steingart K, Shah M. 2021.
- 330 Impact of diagnostic strategies for tuberculosis using lateral flow urine
- 331 lipoarabinomannan assay in people living with HIV. *Cochrane Database of Systematic*
- 332 *Reviews* 2021 (8): CD014641.
- 333 12. Muyoyeta M, Kerkhoff AD, Chilukutu L, Moreau E, Schumacher SG, Ruhwald M. 2021.
- 334 Diagnostic accuracy of a novel point-of-care urine lipoarabinomannan assay for the

- 335 detection of tuberculosis among adult outpatients in Zambia: a prospective cross-
336 sectional study. *Eur Respir J* 58.
- 337 13. LaCourse SM, Seko E, Wood R, Bundi W, Ouma GS, Agaya J, Richardson BA, John-Stewart
338 G, Wandiga S, Cangelosi GA. 2022. Diagnostic performance of oral swabs for non-
339 sputum based TB diagnosis in a TB/HIV endemic setting. *PLoS One* 17:e0262123.
- 340 14. Wood RC, Andama A, Hermansky G, Burkot S, Asege L, Job M, Katumba D, Nakaye M,
341 Mwebe SZ, Mulondo J, Bachman CM, Nichols KP, Le Ny A-LM, Ortega C, Olson RN,
342 Weigel KM, Olson AM, Madan D, Bell D, Cattamanchi A, Worodria W, Semitala FC,
343 Somoskovi A, Cangelosi GA, Minch KJ. 2021. Characterization of oral swab samples for
344 diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis. *PLOS ONE* 16:e0251422.
- 345 15. Luabeya AK, Wood RC, Shenje J, Filander E, Ontong C, Mabwe S, Africa H, Nguyen FK,
346 Olson A, Weigel KM, Jones-Engel L, Hatherill M, Cangelosi GA. 2019. Noninvasive
347 Detection of Tuberculosis by Oral Swab Analysis. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*
348 57:e01847-18.
- 349 16. Wood RC, Luabeya AK, Weigel KM, Wilbur AK, Jones-Engel L, Hatherill M, Cangelosi GA.
350 2015. Detection of Mycobacterium tuberculosis DNA on the oral mucosa of tuberculosis
351 patients. *Sci Rep* 5: 8668.
- 352 17. Nicol MP, Wood RC, Workman L, Prins M, Whitman C, Ghebrekristos Y, Mbhele S, Olson
353 A, Jones-Engel LE, Zar HJ, Cangelosi GA. 2019. Microbiological diagnosis of pulmonary
354 tuberculosis in children by oral swab polymerase chain reaction. *Scientific Reports*
355 9:10789.
- 356 18. Valinetz ED, Cangelosi GA. 2021. A Look Inside: Oral Sampling for Detection of Non-Oral
357 Infectious Diseases. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* doi:10.1128/jcm.02360-
358 20:JCM.02360-20.
- 359 19. Flores JA, Calderon R, Mesman AW, Soto M, Coit J, Aliaga J, Mendoza M, Leon SR, Konda
360 K, Mestanza FM, Mendoza CJ, Lecca L, Murray MB, Holmberg RC, Pollock NR, Franke MF.
361 2020. Detection of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis DNA in Buccal Swab Samples from
362 Children in Lima, Peru. *The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal* 39.
- 363 20. Mesman AW, Calderon R, Soto M, Coit J, Aliaga J, Mendoza M, Franke MF. 2019.
364 Mycobacterium tuberculosis detection from oral swabs with Xpert MTB/RIF ULTRA: a
365 pilot study. *BMC Res Notes* 12:349-349.
- 366 21. Song Y, Ma Y, Liu R, Shang Y, Ma L, Huo F, Li Y, Shu W, Wang Y, Gao M, Pang Y. 2021.
367 Diagnostic Yield of Oral Swab Testing by TB-LAMP for Diagnosis of Pulmonary
368 Tuberculosis. *Infection and drug resistance* 14:89-95.
- 369 22. Andama A, Whitman GR, Crowder R, Reza TF, Jaganath D, Mulundo J, Kabuleta TN,
370 Semitala F, Worodria W, Cook C, Wood RC, Weigel K, Olson AM, Lohmiller Shaw J,
371 Denkinger C, Nahid P, Cangelosi G, Cattamanchi A. 2022. Accuracy of tongue swab
372 testing using Xpert MTB-RIF Ultra for tuberculosis diagnosis. *J Clin Microbiol*, in press.
373

374 **Table 1. Participant clinical and laboratory characteristics**
 375

	Total	TB case^a	Not TB case
	N=131	N=64	N=67
Gender, N(%)			
female	59 (45)	28 (44)	31 (46)
male	72 (55)	36 (56)	36 (54)
Age, median (IQR)	36 (31-46)	35 (28-49)	37 (33-46)
HIV status, N (%)			
negative	10 (8)	10 (16)	0 (0)
positive	121 (92)	54 (84)	67 (100)
CD4+ T-cell count, median (IQR) ^b	115 (37-319)	89 (40-227)	257 (100-551)
Cough present, N (%)	98 (75)	56 (88)	42 (63)
Any TB symptom present ^c , N (%)	128 (97)	64 (100)	64 (96)
Urine LF-LAM ^d positive, N(%)	22 (17)	22 (34)	0 (0)
OSA positive, N (%) Cq<32	27 (21)	25 (39)	2 (3)
OSA positive, N (%) Cq<38	57 (44)	42 (65)	15 (22)
Xpert Ultra Ct, median (IQR) ^e		16.5 (15.9-20.8)	-

376 ^aTB case = reference sputum TB positive (Xpert Ultra and/or culture). ^bHIV-positive participants only; data
 377 available for N=105. ^cTB symptoms queried: cough, weight loss, fevers/chills, loss of appetite, fatigue. ^dLF-LAM,
 378 lateral flow lipoarabinomannan test. ^eCycle threshold (Ct) values available for 60/62 positive Xpert Ultra results.

379
 380
 381
 382
 383
 384
 385
 386
 387
 388

Table 2. Sensitivity and specificity of non-sputum tests alone or in combination, compared to TB reference standard (sputum Xpert Ultra or sputum culture).

	Sensitivity	Specificity
Tongue Swab (OSA) Cq<32	25/64 (39%)	65/67 (97%)
Tongue Swab (OSA) Cq<38	42/64 (67%)	52/67 (78%)
Urine LF-LAM ^a	22/63 (35%)	67/67 (100%)
LAM or OSA ^b _{Cq<32}	36/63 (57%)	65/67 (97%)
LAM or OSA ^b _{Cq<38}	45/63 (71%)	52/67 (78%)

389 ^aLF-LAM, lateral flow lipoarabinomannan test
 390 ^bOSA: Tongue swab tested by manual qPCR using 2 thresholds of positivity: Cq<38 (liberal) and
 391 Cq<32 (stringent).
 392
 393

394 **Table 3. Sputum Xpert Ultra signal strength in tongue swab (OSA)-positive versus urine**
 395 **LAM-positive patients.**

	Urine LAM-positive (regardless of OSA result)	OSA-positive (regardless of urine LAM result)	Urine LAM-positive, OSA-negative	OSA-positive, urine LAM- negative
N	21	23	11	13
Mean sputum Cq*	17.66	16.43	18.73	16.39
Standard deviation	2.69	1.55	3.15	1.71

396 *Value reported by Xpert Ultra, IS6110/IS 1081 combined probe

397

398 **Table 4. Diagnostic performance of Xpert Ultra and manual qPCR on 18 tongue swab**
 399 **samples, compared to TB reference sputum testing (ref).**

Tongue swab subset (N=18)	TB ref* positive	TB ref negative
OSA Xpert Ultra positive	10**	0
OSA Xpert Ultra negative	0	7
OSA qPCR _{Cq<32} positive	11	2
OSA qPCR _{Cq<32} negative	0	5

400 *Ref: Reference sputum Xpert Ultra or culture positive.

401 **One patient with TB ref+ sputum sample had an invalid result by tongue swab Xpert Ultra.

402

403

404

405 **Figure legend**

406

407 **Figure 1. Venn diagram showing overlap of the 2 non-sputum tests (tongue swab and**
408 **urine LAM) and the sputum tuberculosis reference (Xpert Ultra or tuberculosis culture).**

409 The number of positive participants falling within each category is shown (N=131 participants).

410 LF-LAM, lateral flow lipoarabinomannan test. *One sputum reference+/tongue swab- participant
411 had an invalid LAM result.

412

413

414

415

416

